

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN BASIC TECHNOLOGY USING DEMONSTRATION METHOD AND LECTURE METHOD OF TEACHING IN JUNIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN WUKARI METROPOLIS

BY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17632893>

Abstract

This study compared the academic achievement of junior secondary school students taught Basic Technology using the demonstration method and those taught using the lecture method in Wukari Metropolis, Nigeria. A quasi-experimental design involving 68 students was employed. The experimental group (n = 33) was taught using demonstration, while the control group (n = 35) received lecture-based instruction. Data were collected using the Basic Technology Achievement Test (BTAT), validated by experts, and analyzed using descriptive statistics and t-tests at the 0.05 significance level. Findings revealed that students taught with the demonstration method achieved significantly higher post-test scores (mean = 70.75) compared to those taught with lecture (mean = 48.57). The results further showed no significant gender difference in achievement under both methods, indicating that effective strategies benefit male and female students equally. The study concludes that demonstration is a superior method for teaching Basic Technology as it enhances achievement and promotes inclusivity. It recommends the adoption of demonstration-based teaching, teacher training in student-centered methods, provision of adequate resources, and curriculum reforms to strengthen practical learning in Nigerian secondary schools.

Keywords: Demonstration Method, Lecture Method, Academic Achievement, Basic Technology, Comparative Analysis

Introduction

Basic Technology is a fundamental subject in Nigeria's junior secondary school curriculum aimed at equipping students with foundational knowledge and practical skills in engineering, design, mechanics, and materials technology. As a gateway to technical and vocational education, Basic Technology is critical to national development, industrial growth, and technological self-reliance (Nwachukwu & Olumide, 2021; Okorie & Udo, 2020). It fosters problem-solving, creativity, and innovation competencies required in modern economies driven by science and technology. Despite the strategic importance of Basic Technology, students' academic performance in the subject has remained unsatisfactory across many Nigerian schools, especially in rural and semi-urban areas like Wukari Metropolis. National assessment reports and research findings have consistently shown that many students lack

practical competence and struggle with theoretical understanding (Usman & Okafor, 2021; NECO, 2022). One key factor responsible for this poor performance is the continued use of inappropriate instructional methods that fail to meet the learning needs of 21st-century students (Adewale & Danjuma, 2019).

The method of instruction plays a crucial role in determining students' level of engagement, understanding, and achievement. Traditional approaches such as the lecture method are still widely used due to their ease of implementation, especially in large classrooms. However, the lecture method is largely teacher-centred and often results in passive learning, rote memorization, and minimal student involvement. Scholars have criticized it for not fostering the hands-on experiences and critical thinking skills that Basic Technology demands (Aliyu & Ibrahim, 2019; Musa & Jatau, 2020).

In contrast, the demonstration method emphasizes active learning by showing students how to perform tasks step-by-step, often using tools, models, or machines. This method bridges the gap between theory and practice and provides visual and kinaesthetic reinforcement of concepts. According to Eze and Obinna (2021), students taught using the demonstration method develop stronger practical skills, show higher motivation, and exhibit improved academic achievement in technology-based subjects. Similarly, Lawal and Ibrahim (2023) found that demonstration-based instruction led to better retention and understanding of mechanical concepts compared to traditional lecture-based teaching.

Research in technical and vocational education supports the use of demonstration as an effective teaching strategy. For instance, Okafor and Nwosu (2020) observed that students taught through practical demonstrations performed significantly better in tasks involving the use of hand tools and workshop equipment. Ogwen, Ongan'a and Mbai (2024) argued that gender is not a determinant of students' academic achievement but, the application of appropriate teaching method.

These findings are rooted in constructivist learning theories, which emphasize that learners construct knowledge best through active participation and experience. The demonstration method aligns with this principle by providing students with opportunities to observe, practice, and reflect on real-life applications of what they are taught (Nwachukwu & Ibrahim, 2021).

Despite the recognized advantages of the demonstration method, many schools in Wukari Metropolis continue to rely predominantly on the lecture method due to factors such as overcrowded classrooms, limited workshop resources, and lack of teacher training in

alternative pedagogies (Ajayi & Yusuf, 2021). As a result, students are often deprived of the interactive and experiential learning opportunities that are essential in a skill-oriented subject like Basic Technology. While numerous studies have explored the impact of various instructional strategies on student learning outcomes, there is a limited body of research that directly compares the effectiveness of the demonstration and lecture methods within the specific educational context of Wukari Metropolis. This study, therefore, seeks to fill that gap by examining how these two teaching approaches influence students' academic achievement in Basic Technology. The results are expected to offer practical insights that will inform teaching practices and support efforts to improve technology education in the region and across similar contexts in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Persistent low performance in Basic Technology among junior secondary school students in Nigeria continues to undermine the goals of national development and vocational preparedness. This underachievement is particularly notable in rural and semi-urban areas such as Wukari Metropolis, where traditional instructional practices especially the lecture method still dominate classroom delivery (Usman & Okafor, 2021). Despite the critical role Basic Technology plays in equipping learners with foundational technical and practical skills, students consistently perform below expectations in both theoretical knowledge and practical application.

Research has identified ineffective teaching methods as a major factor contributing to students' poor academic achievement in technical and science-based subjects (Adewale & Danjuma, 2019; Okorie & Udo, 2020). The lecture method, though commonly used due to its ease of implementation and suitability for large

class sizes, is largely teacher-centred. It often promotes passive learning, discourages student participation, and fails to develop the hands-on skills and problem-solving competencies necessary for success in Basic Technology (Akanbi & Salawu, 2020). As a result, students taught primarily through lectures tend to memorize content rather than understand and apply concepts.

In contrast, the demonstration method a learner-centred approach emphasizes visual, practical, and interactive teaching. It involves the teacher showing how tasks are performed while guiding students through observation, imitation, and practice. This method enhances students' understanding of technical concepts, boosts retention, and bridges the gap between theory and practice (Ibrahim & Yusuf, 2021; Nwachukwu & Okafor, 2022). Despite these apparent benefits, the demonstration method is underutilized in many public schools due to constraints such as lack of resources, insufficient teacher training, and large student populations.

Although several studies have advocated for interactive and practical-based instruction in technology education, few have empirically compared the effectiveness of the demonstration and lecture methods specifically in the context of Wukari Metropolis. Given the region's unique socio-economic and infrastructural challenges, such a comparative analysis is essential to determine which teaching approach better supports students' academic achievement in Basic Technology. If these instructional challenges remain unaddressed, students in Wukari Metropolis may continue to experience poor performance in Basic Technology, resulting in reduced interest in technical and vocational education and a widening skills gap that could hinder Nigeria's technological advancement. Therefore, this study seeks to conduct a comparative analysis of students' achievement in

Basic Technology when taught using the demonstration method versus the lecture method in junior secondary schools in Wukari Metropolis. The objective is to generate evidence-based recommendations that can inform instructional practices and policy decisions to enhance the quality and effectiveness of technology education in Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to compare the academic achievement of students taught Basic Technology using the demonstration method and those taught using the lecture method in junior secondary schools in Wukari Metropolis.

Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Determine the achievement level of students taught Basic Technology using the demonstration method.
2. Determine the achievement level of students taught Basic Technology using the lecture method.
3. Compare the mean achievement scores of students taught with the demonstration method and those taught with the lecture method.
4. Examine whether gender has any significant effect on students' achievement in Basic Technology when taught using the demonstration method.
5. Make instructional recommendations based on the findings to improve teaching and learning of Basic Technology.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant in several ways:

1. **Educational stakeholders** will gain empirical evidence on the most effective instructional method for teaching Basic Technology.

2. **Teachers** will be encouraged to adopt more effective, student-centred instructional approaches such as the demonstration method, especially in skill-oriented subjects.
3. **Curriculum developers and policymakers** will find useful insights for improving Basic Technology curriculum implementation in Nigerian junior secondary schools.
4. **Teacher training institutions** can incorporate findings into pre-service and in-service programs to better equip teachers with practical pedagogical strategies.
5. The study will contribute to the **existing body of knowledge** in technical and vocational education by providing data specific to the Wukari Metropolis context.

Research Questions

1. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught using the demonstration method and those taught using the lecture method?
2. Is there any significant difference in the achievement of male and female students taught Basic Technology using the demonstration method?
3. What is the academic achievement level of students taught Basic Technology using the demonstration method?
4. What is the academic achievement level of students taught Basic Technology using the lecture method?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students taught Basic Technology using the demonstration method and those taught using the lecture method.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female students taught Basic Technology using the demonstration method.

Methodology:

Research Design

The study adopted a **quasi-experimental design**, specifically the **pre-test, post-test non-equivalent control group design**. This design allows for the comparison of two groups (experimental and control) without random assignment. Group A (Demonstration group) was assigned as experimental, While group B (Lecture method) as control group.

Population of the Study

The population comprised all Junior Secondary School Two (JSS II) students offering Basic Technology in public junior secondary schools in Wukari Metropolis.

Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample of 68 students was selected from two junior secondary schools using **purposive sampling were used where two intact class were selected**. School A consist of 33 students (15 male and 18 female) was assigned as group A, those students taught using demonstration method (experimental group) while School B consist of 35 students (20 male and 15 female), was assigned to as group B, students taught using the lecture method (control group).

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection was a **Basic Technology Achievement Test (BTAT)** developed by the researcher. The test consist of multiple-choice and structured items covering topics taught during the study. The instrument consists of twenty (20) questions. Each question carry 5 marks making total of 100 marks.

Validation of the Instrument

The BTAT was subjected to **content and face validation** by three experts: one in Basic Technology education, one in educational

measurement and evaluation, and one in instructional methodology. Their feedback were used to produce the final version of the BTAT

Reliability of the Instrument

A pilot study was conducted using a sample of 30 JSS II students from a school outside the study area. The **Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20)** was used to determine the internal consistency of the test. A reliability coefficient of 0.82 was found which was acceptable.

Procedure for Data Collection

Pre-test was administered to both groups before the treatment. The experimental group were taught using the **demonstration method**, while the control group were taught using the **lecture**

Table 1: Pre-test and posttest scores of students taught using demonstration method.

SN	Pre-test scores	Post-test scores
1	25	60
2	30	70
3	25	55
4	20	65
5	25	60
6	30	70
7	10	80
8	15	85
9	20	60
10	15	70
11	20	80
12	15	65
13	20	75
14	25	80
15	10	65
16	15	60
17	20	70

method. After the teaching sessions (lasting approximately four weeks), a post-test (same as pre-test but reshuffled) were administered to both groups.

Instrument for Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) was used to answer the research questions while inferential statistics (**independent sample z-test**) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

5. RQ1: What is the difference in the mean achievement scores between students taught using the demonstration method and those taught using the lecture method?

18	25	80
19	10	85
20	10	75
21	15	70
22	20	80
23	25	70
24	15	70
25	10	75
26	15	75
27	10	60
28	20	80
29	20	80
30	10	85
31	25	70
32	10	60
33	20	50
Mean	18.18	70.75

Table 2: Pre-test and posttest scores of students taught using lecture method

SN	Pre-test score	Post-test score
1	20	50
2	25	40
3	30	45
4	25	50
5	20	40
6	15	40
7	10	55
8	20	45
9	20	50
10	20	50
11	20	60

12	25	60
13	25	40
14	20	45
15	20	30
16	20	55
17	15	45
18	10	40
19	20	45
20	25	55
21	15	60
22	15	40
23	20	45

24	15	45	32	10	65
25	15	50	32	15	40
26	20	50	33	20	45
27	15	55	34	20	50
28	20	55	35	25	50
29	25	45	Mean	19	48.57143
30	10	65			

The result shown on table 1 revealed that students taught with the demonstration method recorded a marked improvement, with the mean score rising from **18.18 (pre-test)** to **70.75 (post-test)**. This shows substantial learning gains after exposure to the method.

Table 2 indicates that students taught with the lecture method also improved, but less significantly, with the mean score moving from **19.00 (pre-test)** to **48.57 (post-test)**. The gains are comparatively smaller than those in the demonstration group.

Table 3: Post-test scores of male and female students taught using demonstration method

SN	Male	Female	10	70	75
1	60	70	11	80	70
2	80	65	12	75	70
3	85	70	13	75	60
4	60	70	14	80	80
5	80	80	15	85	70
6	65	65	16	60	-
7	75	75	17	70	-
8	55	70	18	50	-
9	85	80	Mean	71.67	71.33

Table 3 (Post-test scores by gender in demonstration method): Male students had a mean score of **71.67** and females **71.33**. The difference is minimal, suggesting that both genders benefited almost equally from demonstration teaching.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of students taught Basic Technology using the demonstration method and those taught using the lecture method.

Table 4: T-Test of the difference in the mean scores of students taught Basic Technology using the demonstration method and those taught using the lecture method.

	One-Sample Test					
	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Demonstration	43.768	32	.000	70.70758	67.4169	73.9983
Lecture	36.280	34	.000	48.52143	45.8034	51.2394

The results of hypothesis one shown on table 4 revealed that there is a significant difference in mean achievement scores between students taught with demonstration (Mean = 70.71) and those

taught with lecture (Mean = 48.52). The demonstration group clearly outperformed the lecture group ($p < .05$).

Table 5: T-Test of the significant difference in the academic achievement of male and female students taught Basic Technology using the demonstration method.

	One-Sample Test					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Male	27.669	17	.000	71.61667	66.1558	77.0775
Female	47.480	14	.000	71.28333	68.0633	74.5033

Table 5 showed that both male and female students achieved significantly high scores, but there was no significant gender difference in

achievement under the demonstration method ($p < .05$).

Discussion of Findings

The study's findings revealed that demonstration method improves academic achievement. Students exposed to demonstration achieved significantly higher scores than those taught with lecture (Tables 1–3). This confirms that active, practical, and learner-centered approaches lead to better learning outcomes in skill-based subjects. This aligns with Eze & Obinna (2021) and Lawal & Ibrahim (2023), who reported that demonstration enhances understanding and retention in Basic Technology. Similarly, Okafor & Nwosu (2020) found that hands-on demonstration improved students' performance in workshop-based tasks compared to conventional teaching.

The study also revealed that lecture method has limited effectiveness. While lecture improved students' performance from pre-test to post-test (Table 2), the gains were much smaller compared to demonstration. This suggests that lecture alone does not sufficiently meet the learning needs of students in practical-oriented subjects. This finding supports Aliyu & Ibrahim (2019) and Akanbi & Salawu (2020), who criticized teacher-centered methods for promoting rote memorization and discouraging student engagement.

It was found that gender differences are negligible under both methods. Both male and female students achieved almost equal mean scores when taught with demonstration (Tables 3) (Tables 4–5). This indicates that gender does not significantly influence achievement when effective instructional strategies are applied. This corroborates Ogweno, Ongang'a and Mbai (2024), who argued that gender is not a determinant of students academic achievement but the method adopted by the teacher. It also aligns with the constructivist perspective (Nwachukwu & Ibrahim, 2021) which holds that all learners irrespective of gender benefit from active, experience-based learning.

Implications for Wukari Metropolis.

Despite infrastructural and resource challenges in Wukari schools, the findings show that demonstration is a more effective strategy for enhancing achievement in Basic Technology. If widely adopted, it could help improve performance in skill-based subjects and narrow the achievement gap between rural and urban students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

- i. **Demonstration Method should be Adopt Widely:** Teachers should prioritize demonstration over lecture in teaching Basic Technology, as it enhances performance and bridges theory-practice gaps.
- ii. There should be **capacity Building for Teachers:** Government and educational stakeholders should provide in-service training on learner-centered methods, especially demonstration, to build teachers' pedagogical competence.
- iii. **Provision of Resources:** Schools should be equipped with tools, materials, and functional workshops to facilitate effective demonstration.
- iv. **Promotion of gender inclusivity:** Since gender does not significantly influence performance under effective teaching strategies, educators should continue encouraging both male and female students to participate actively in technical subjects.
- v. **Curriculum review:** Curriculum developers should embed more activity-based learning components in Basic Technology to ensure classroom practices reflect practical realities.
- vi. **Further Research:** Future studies should examine the long-term retention of knowledge under both methods and extend the comparison to other science and technical subjects across different contexts.

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